

Making things new: Invention privileges and the configuration of priority

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Abstract

It was because of the early modern system of invention privileges that questions concerning inventorship became a recurrent subject matter of legal dispute. This essay focuses mainly on the details of one such dispute, namely the 1597 case litigated in the Dutch Republic between Jacob Floris van Langren (ca. 1525–1610) and Jodocus Hondius Sr. (1563–1612). The essay assesses how the law shaped, challenged, and constrained claims to innovation, pushing the argument that it was because of the privilege system that the borders between imitation and novelty became ever more clearly defined. The case study thus illustrates how the law functioned as a technology ordering a complex web of knowledge and status claims.

Keywords

Dutch Republic, early modern, invention privileges, inventive step, inventorship, Jacob Floris van Langren, Jodocus Hondius, legal technology, non-obviousness, patents

Introduction

This essay revolves around a legal dispute over the nature of early modern invention privileges. These privileges were, in many ways, the precursors of what we call “patents” today; they were temporary exclusive rights that allowed, under a specific set of conditions, for the commercial exploitation of new and useful ideas in the field of technology.¹

1. For a brief comparative overview of the history of invention privileges, see Carlo Marco Belfanti, “Between Mercantilism and Market: Privileges for Invention in Early Modern Europe,” *Journal of Institutional Economics* 2, no. 3 (2006): 319–38. For some of the

In contrast to modern patents, however, the entitlement to claim a privilege was not a right. Privileges were gifts bestowed by the authorities, legitimizing an exception to the common process of law.² In practice, it meant that the “first finder” of a new method or a new machine was temporarily allowed to establish an economic monopoly (mostly for the duration of ten to twenty years). Whereas monopolies were otherwise condemned as unlawful interventions in the natural course of the economy, state-licensed monopolies legitimized by invention privileges were justified on the basis of the notion that the introduction of new technologies was to the advantage of the general public.

In that context, the category of “novelty” had a very specific meaning. Privileges had a local validity that was determined by the scope of the sovereign power. As a result, it was of lesser importance whether or not the inventor had first conceived of the idea behind an invention. What mattered was that an inventor was the first to practice a certain craft within the jurisdiction of the privilege-granting authority; that he would be the first to reveal the technical details of an invention and thus render the invention useful to the local economy. Novelty, it can thus be said, was not understood in a temporal sense but geographically determined on a case-by-case basis.

The transformation toward a universal understanding of novelty occurred only in the course of the nineteenth century with the reconceptualization of the inventor as an individual genius creating technological ideas.³ Mario Biagioli has connected this shift to the introduction of patent specifications in the 1790s that “reframed both the spatial and temporal dimensions of the patent.”⁴ Once the authorities required the submission of specifications that described an invention “in such full, clear, concise, and exact terms as to enable any person skilled in the art [...] to make and use the same,” it became possible to determine the substantial novelty of an invention by setting off those specifications to earlier publications, collectively referred to as prior art.⁵ Eventually, the modern notion

discrepancies between early modern privileges and modern patents, see Mario Biagioli, “Patent Specification and Political Representation: How Patents Became Rights,” in Mario Biagioli, Peter Jaszi, and Martha Woodmansee (eds.), *Making and Unmaking Intellectual Property* (Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press, 2011), pp.25–40.

2. For an excellent overview on the various forms of privilege, see Barbara Dölemeyer and Heinz Mohnhaupt (eds.), *Das Privileg im europäischen Vergleich*, 2 vols. (Frankfurt am Main: Klostermann, 1997–9).
3. Oren Bracha, “Geniuses and Owners: The Construction of Inventors and the Emergence of American Intellectual Property,” in Daniel W Hamilton (ed.), *Transformations in American Legal History: Essays in Honor of Professor Morton J. Horwitz*, Vol. 1 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard Law School, 2010), pp.369–90. On the nineteenth-century figure of the inventor as a genius, see Christine MacLeod, *Heroes of Invention: Technology, Liberalism and British Identity, 1750-1914* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007).
4. Mario Biagioli, “Patent Republic: Representing Inventions, Constructing Rights and Authors,” *Social Research: An International Quarterly of Social Sciences* 73, no. 4 (2006): 1129–72, 1153.
5. The regulation has been codified in 35 U.S.C. § 112. Prior art searches are an essential part of modern patent granting procedure; if an invention has been described in the prior art, a patent on that invention is not valid. Prior art consists of all the information available to the public in any form prior to the patent application.

of invention crystallized around the notion of “non-obviousness” in the United States and that of “inventive step” in Europe. In addition to novelty and utility, non-obviousness requires a sufficient “degree of skill and ingenuity” as a condition for patentability,⁶ which is comparable to the inventive step’s requirement that an invention should not be obvious to the skilled person in the light of the state of the art.⁷

This article contributes to an archeology of the modern notion of invention as connected to ingenuity and inventiveness rather than older concepts of invention rooted in utility or local novelty.⁸ Guided by accounts that mainly focus on Italy and Germany, the dominant consensus is that some concept of ingenuity was initially present in the earliest patent systems dating from the fifteenth century, but faded away in the following centuries, only to be taken up again in the 1800s.⁹ A detailed reconstruction of a pivotal late sixteenth-century Dutch case indicates that the consensus view needs revision. Ingenuity and inventiveness were always key to patenting, though their role was often occluded by the more conspicuous role that utility played at that time in determining who the “first and true inventor” was.¹⁰

6. The expression “degree of skill and ingenuity” comes from the Supreme Court’s decision in *Hotchkiss v. Greenwood* 52 US 248 (1850), at p.267. This landmark case is usually seen at the basis for the non-obviousness requirement, later codified in 35 U.S.C. § 103. It is important to note that novelty is different from obviousness; an invention can be new but obvious, and therefore not eligible for patent protection. For a detailed reconstruction of *Hotchkiss v. Greenwood*, see Kenneth J. Burchfiel, “Revising the ‘Original’ Patent Clause: Pseudohistory in Constitutional Construction,” *Harvard Journal of Law and Technology* 2 (1989): 155–218.
7. EPC Art. 52(1); EPC Art. 56. Non-obviousness and the inventive step may be considered synonymous according to the 1994 TRIPS agreement, which laid down the framework for intellectual property regimes around the world. TRIPS Agreement Art 27(1), note 5. Provided that the subject matter is susceptible of patent protection and that sufficient disclosure has been provided, inventions must thus be new, useful (capable of industrial application), and involve an inventive step to satisfy the requirements for patentability.
8. For historical and conceptual explorations of the notion of invention in modern patent law, see Lionel Bently and Brad Sherman, *The Making of Modern Intellectual Property Law: The British Experience* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1999); Oren Bracha, *Owning Ideas: The Intellectual Origins of American Intellectual Property, 1790–1909* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2016); Biagioli, “Patent Specification and Political Representation” (note 1); Alain Pottage and Brad Sherman, *Figures of Invention: A History of Modern Patent Law* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2010).
9. John F. Duffy, “Inventing Invention: A Case Study of Legal Innovation,” *Texas Law Review* 86, no. 1 (2007): 1–72, 15. Scholars defending a similar position include F. K. Beier, “The Inventive Step in its Historical Development,” *IIC International Review of Industrial Property and Copyright Law* 17, no. 3 (1986): 301–23; L. W. P. Pessers, “The Evolution of the Inventiveness Requirement” (Diss. University of Amsterdam, 2015). An important exception is provided by Mario Biagioli, who argued that the inventive faculty was fully irrelevant for the functioning of early modern patent regimes. Biagioli, “Patent Republic,” 1145–6 (note 4).
10. The expression “first and true inventor” comes from the 1624 Statute of Monopolies. A digital copy of the statute can be found online at “Statute of Monopolies, Westminster (1624),” in L. Bently & M. Kretschmer (eds.), *Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900)*, <www.copyrighthistory.org> (July 4, 2017).

The case at hand is the 1597 lawsuit between the globemakers Jacob Floris van Langren (ca. 1525–1610) and Jodocus Hondius Sr. (1563–1612). This conflict has previously been studied in detail by Peter Van der Krogt, who embedded it in a broader context of competition between different Dutch globe-producing firms.¹¹ I shall give more attention to the language used by the different stakeholders to demarcate the nature of their invention, emphasizing the various rhetorical strategies used by inventors to render themselves into the authors of their invention.

In doing so, I build upon a small but important body of literature exploring the social-epistemological fabrication of fundamental notions in modern patent law. Whereas some have emphasized the strategies employed by inventors to nest their claims,¹² others have focused on the question of how the categories of novelty and obviousness were negotiated in and around the courtroom.¹³ The common denominator in this literature is the argument that legal categories, often with far-reaching consequences, are not ontologically predetermined but come about in an unsettled process of negotiation. In that process, the use of language plays an essential role. I am particularly indebted on this point to the insights provided by Charles Bazerman, who has examined modern patents in terms of a “genre” that frames social action.¹⁴ Early modern invention privileges equally

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11. Petrus C.J. van der Krogt, *Globi Neerlandici: De globeproductie in de Nederlanden* (Utrecht: HES, 1989), pp.107–10, 355–69. Reproduced in English as Peter van der Krogt, *Globi Neerlandici: The Production of Globes in the Low Countries* (Utrecht: Hes & De Graaf, 1993). For the reproduction and translation into English of the documents related to the conflict, see *ibid.*, pp.576–9, 583–617. I have used the original documents for my research, and all translations of the source material are my own. Information on this case can be found in a file that is kept in the Dutch National Archives, The Hague (hereafter NL-HaNA), States-General, 1.01.02, inv.nr. 12550.28. This file contains several loose sections, without page numbering. For the reader’s convenience, a reference is included to the title of the individual sections as well as to the reproduction in the English version of the book by Van der Krogt (hereafter abbreviated as PVDK).
 12. Geof Bowker, “What Is a Patent?” in Wiebe E. Bijker and John Law (eds.), *Shaping Technology/ Building Society: Studies in Sociotechnical Change* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1992), pp.53–74; Greg Myers, “From Discovery to Invention: The Writing and Rewriting of Two Patents,” *Social Studies of Science* 25, no. 1 (1995): 57–105.
 13. Alberto Cambrosio, Peter Keating, and Michael Mackenzie, “Scientific Practice in the Courtroom: The Construction of Sociotechnical Identities in a Biotechnology Patent Dispute,” *Social Problems* 37, no. 3 (1990): 275–93; David P. Miller, “Watt in Court: Specifying Steam Engines and Classifying Engineers in the Patent Trials of the 1790s,” *History of Technology* 27 (2006): 43–76; Amit Prasad, “The (Amorphous) Anatomy of an Invention: The Case of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI),” *Social Studies of Science* 37, no. 4 (2007): 533–60.
 14. Charles Bazerman, *The Languages of Edison’s Light* (Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press, 1999), in particular chapters 5 and 12. See also Charles Bazerman, “Systems of Genres and the Enactment of Social Intentions,” in A. Freedman and P. Medway (eds.), *Genre and the New Rhetoric* (London: Taylor & Francis, 1994), pp.79–101; Dan L. Burk and Jessica Reyman, “Patents as Genre: A Prospectus,” *Law & Literature* 26, no. 2 (2014): 163–90.

constituted a genre that entailed techniques to organize, sort, chart, and classify claims to innovation in the domain of knowledge. Along these lines, the documents related to *Van Langren v. Hondius* show how the language of the law both constructed as well as stabilized the categories of novelty and invention. I develop this thought further after a brief introduction to the privilege system in the Dutch Republic, as I enter into the conflict between the two globemakers and highlight how early modern legal protocol related to the configuration of priority.

Setting the scene: invention privileges in the Dutch Republic

A Dutch system of invention privileges came into being soon after the de facto independence of the Republic in 1581, that is to say at the height of the Dutch Revolt (ca. 1568–1648).¹⁵ To a large degree, the system developed in the Dutch Republic was a continuation of the system that had been in place in the Spanish Habsburg Empire, except that privileges were no longer issued in the name of an overlord. Instead, invention privileges were issued predominantly on two different levels: at the provincial level by the Assembly of the States-Provincial (in which the cities, the nobility, and occasionally other parties were represented) and at the federal level by the Assembly of the States-General (in which each of the seven provinces that constituted the Republic was represented with one vote).¹⁶ The scope of the jurisdiction of the issuing authorities determined the validity of privileges. Thus, for illustration, a privilege issued by the States of Holland was not valid in the Province of Utrecht, and a privilege issued by the States-General was valid in each of the seven provinces, but not in the Kingdom of France or the Holy Roman Empire.

Up until the 1640s, the introduction of new inventions in the Dutch Republic was usually dealt with by the States-General, which issued on average between five and fifteen privileges per year.¹⁷ Most of these privileges related to inventions in the field of military technology (such as canons, guns, and pikes), hydraulics (pumps, dredging equipment, and so on), urban welfare (fire-extinguishers, bridges, and so on), and industrial technology (furnaces, stoves, industrial mills, and so on). The system of invention privileges in the Dutch Republic essentially was not that

15. For the emergence of a Dutch system of invention privileges, see Marius Buning, “Privileged Knowledge. Inventions and the Legitimization of Knowledge in the Early Dutch Republic (1581-1621)” (Diss. European University Institute, 2013); Karel Davids, “Patents and Patentees in the Dutch Republic between c. 1580 and 1720,” *History and Technology* 16, no. 3 (2000): 263–84; Gerard Doorman, *Octrooien voor uitvindingen in de Nederlanden uit de 16e-18e eeuw: Met bespreking van enkele onderwerpen uit de geschiedenis der techniek* (The Hague: Nijhoff, 1940).

16. Although it did happen sporadically, cities in the Dutch Republic hardly ever issued invention privileges on their own authority. They did conclude agreements with the inventors to make sure that they would implement new inventions within city walls. On this issue, see Buning, “Privileged Knowledge,” pp.48–53 (note 15).

17. For an overview of the amount of privileges, inventors, and so on and so forth, see Davids, “Patents and Patentees” (note 15).

different from the schemes that existed, for instance, in England, France, or the Italian city states; issuing exclusive privileges to inventors was part of a curious transformation in European thought, whereby technological advancement was related to the increased production of goods, economic progress, and a notion of world dominance.

Still, the political leadership was cautious about distributing exclusive rights to individuals. It was feared that issuing too many invention privileges might lead to social upheaval, since these privileges led to economic monopolies that could cause a disturbance of the just price.¹⁸ To counteract abuse, the Dutch put in place an examination procedure as well. Prior to the distribution of rights for the commercial exploitation of an invention, the authorities would ask skilled experts for advice covering the functionality of a particular invention, or they would inquire among parties affected by the privilege (such as guild representatives and urban magistrates) whether the new invention would negatively impact existing trade. The utility of an invention was thus established on a local level, and the issue of prior art was not in any way central to the Dutch examination system. Moreover, a number of privileges specifically served to promote inventions designed to imitate products available abroad, as for example a privilege for a method “to bake floor tiles after the Italian way,”¹⁹ or a privilege to produce porcelain that was both in design and in terms of clay “reasonably similar to the porcelain that is coming from far-away strange countries.”²⁰ The unmistakable aim of these invention privileges was to achieve a competitive advantage in a mercantilist framework.²¹ The requirement of “novelty” was purely implemented to make knowledge locally available.

Nonetheless, novelty still had to be proven in legal terms. This was done mostly by attaching two affidavits to a privilege request, in which experts in a particular field would attest that an invention was not known in a specific jurisdiction. If, after the privilege was granted, doubts arose over the correctness of these attestations, it was only through litigation that one could challenge the legitimacy of an inventor’s claim. To illustrate the

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18. Obviously, there were many variations in the exact interpretation of monopolies as well as diverging opinions regarding their admissibility. It was always about striking the right balance between the interests of inventors and those of the society at large. Particular attention in the literature has been given to the situation in England, where the generous distribution of monopolies led to various grievances that eventually resulted in the famous Statute of Monopolies (1624).
 19. “vloersteen te backen op d’ Italiaensche maniere.” Doorman, *Octrooien*, p.219 (note 15). For the relation between novelty and imitation in the Dutch privilege business, see Marius Buning, “Between Imitation and Invention. Inventor Privileges and Technological Progress in the Early Dutch Republic (c. 1585–1625),” *Intellectual History Review* 24, no. 3 (2014): 415–27.
 20. “... tamelyck gelyckformich souden wesen porceleyen commende uuyt wyde vreemde Landen.” NL-HaNA, States-General, 1.01.02, inv. no. 12301, fol. 32 (April 4, 1614).
 21. On the relation between mercantilism and invention privileges, see Belfanti, “Between Mercantilism and Market” (note 1); M. Silberstein, *Erfindungsschutz und merkantilistische Gewerbeprivilegien* (Winterhur: Keller, 1961).

importance of such cases in stabilizing the language of invention as well as shaping notions of priority, I now go into the details of the legal conflict that emerged toward the end of the sixteenth century between two of the most famous globemakers in the Northern Low Countries: *Van Langren v. Hondius*.

The 1597 dispute between Van Langren and Hondius

Jacob Floris van Langren was a pioneer who had been producing globes in the Northern Provinces since the mid-1580s. He was the head of a family dynasty, who often worked together with his sons Arnold and Hendrik in the production of sophisticatedly decorated spheres.²² In contrast, Jodocus Hondius Sr. was a Calvinist from the Southern Netherlands, who had worked briefly for the Duke of Parma before moving to England in 1584 to escape religious persecution. There, he was in contact with a circle of savants, artisans, and adventurers before relocating to Amsterdam in 1593, where he was successful in setting up an important shop selling navigational items.²³

Shortly after his arrival in the Republic, Hondius started working on a terrestrial globe for which the States-General granted him a ten-year privilege on April 1, 1597.²⁴ Within weeks, the Van Langrens tried to stop the production of this globe, appealing to an earlier privilege for the production of globes that had been made out to them by the States-General in September 1592.²⁵ The original complaint by Jacob Floris van Langren and his two sons has, unfortunately, not survived. What remains, however, is a detailed account of Hondius's defense at the States-General, who saw the case through to the end. It often happened that the General Assembly functioned as a court of law in a time when the separation between legislative and judicial powers was still emerging. Yet the fact that the States-General got directly involved with this case shows that it took the matter very seriously. Eventually, it issued a judgment that would fundamentally impact the diffusion of geographical knowledge in the seventeenth century.

The case was triggered when the Van Langrens accused Hondius of piracy, in particular concerning the use and display of specific rhumb lines (a rhumb line, or a loxodrome, is an arc on a chart which intersects all meridians of longitude at the same angle; rhumb lines are especially useful for navigation purposes). In his defense, Hondius drew up a list in which he explained point by point why his globe differed from the globe produced

22. For the Van Langren dynasty see Johannes Keuning, "The Van Langren Family," *Imago Mundi* 13 (1956): 101–9; Van der Krogt, *Globi Neerlandici*, 1989, pp.120–28 (note 11).

23. For Hondius, see Johannes G.C.A. Briels, *Zuidnederlandse boekdrukkers en boekverkopers in de Republiek der Verenigde Nederlanden omstreeks 1570–1630: een bijdrage tot de kennis van de geschiedenis van het boek* (Nieuwkoop: De Graaf, 1974), pp.322–325.

24. PVDK, pp.578–9 (note 11).

25. The privilege had been prolonged for another ten years on January 31, 1596. *Ibid.*, pp.576–8. The first privilege had been issued only to Jacob Floris; the prolongation included the names of his two sons as rightsholders too.

by the Van Langren family.²⁶ For our purposes, there is no need to go into each and every detail of these claims, but it is worthwhile to single out those instances that reveal how Hondius looked at the nature of invention.

Central to Hondius's defense was that the Van Langrens unjustly "claimed that by the power of the privilege that your Excellencies have granted them, anybody is forbidden to produce a globe (even it would be ten times better than theirs), because it is written that no-one can imitate their globe for the time of ten years."²⁷ Hondius sneered that the sheer stupidity of this argumentation was probably due to the fact his opponents were Anabaptists, "heathen and non-baptized."²⁸ The Van Langrens oppressed "all amateurs of the mathematical arts" by claiming infringement upon their privilege.²⁹ For, clearly, the question is "not whether anyone can make a globe, because your Excellencies have proven it to be not so, by granting me a privilege to my work, but only if my globe is made after the globe of my counterparty, or whether my globe resembles it."³⁰

In order to substantiate the claim that his work was new and original, Hondius began by elucidating what a "new invention" actually was. He clarified that certain aspects of a globe dated "from before the time of Christ and shortly after," such as the meridians, the tropics, the polar circles, the general description of lands by Ptolemy, and so forth.³¹ These aspects of the globe could hence not be considered a new invention. The same applied to all the geographical descriptions by Mercator, Ortelius, Postel, and Münster, all of which had been brought to light long before the Van Langrens had ever produced a globe. In conclusion, he claimed that even the use of rhumb lines could not be considered a new invention, since rhumb lines had been "first invented" (*eerst geinventeert*) by Gemma Frisius on a broadsheet and then applied to globes by Mercator, who were both Dutch, for that matter, and whose works had been sold all over the Netherlands.³² Only after "taking away these inventions" could one address the question of "what new invention my counterparty has made and in what aspect I have imitated or followed their invention or works, as they claim."³³

26. *Onderrichtinge Van sulcx als ick vernieut hebbe op myne Globe waer van myne partye gans niet hebben*; PVDK, p.593 (note 11).

27. "...seggende dat door de cracht van t'selve [de Privilegie henlieden by U.E.E. verleent] eenen ygelicken verboden wort eenige globe (of sy schoone 10 mael beter waren als haere) te maken, Daer doch met wtgedruete woorden staet, dat niemant haere globen sal mogen naermaken inde tyt van tien Jaren ofte ... dat niemand hares gelijk synde, sal mogen maken." From Hondius, *Tweede Verantwoordinge*; PVDK, p.595 (note 11).

28. "...heydensche ende ongedoopte syner kinderen." *Ibid.*, p.595.

29. "...alle liefhebbers de Mathematischer consten, souken en verdrucken..." *Ibid.*, p.595.

30. "[De vraag is] niet of yemant anders globen maken magh, want dat hebben U.E.E. anders laten blycken, my ooc privilegie op myn werck verleenende, nemaer alleenlick of myne globe is gemaect naer de globe van myne partye, ofte of myne globe de haere gelyck sy." *Ibid.*, p.595.

31. "... als van voor Christi tyt ende corts daer naer geinventeert syn geweest" *Ibid.*, p.595.

32. *Ibid.*, p.595.

33. "... (dese inventien weggenomen synde) ... wat myne partye voor nieuwe inventien hebbe, Ende warin ick hare inventie ofte wercken naergemaect ofte gevolght hebbe, alsoo zy zeggen." *Ibid.*, p.597.

Hondius went into detail to explain which new inventions could be found on his globe and not on the globe made by the Van Langrens. He highlighted, in particular, the inclusion of new geographical information that had come to light in the face of recent voyages of discovery by the English, the Spanish, and the Dutch. Today, the possibility of claiming geographical data as intellectual property no longer exists; it is generally accepted that the disclosure of something that already exists in nature is a discovery and therefore not patentable.³⁴ In contrast, it was fairly common in the early modern period to conflate notions of “invention” and “discovery” under the umbrella category of “findings” that had come about under the guidance of human intellect. From that perspective, it did not matter whether this meant finding a new trade route, a new land, a new production method, or a new technical device.

Hondius kept insisting that he had corrected many mistakes found in earlier globes, that he had provided more information than his counterparty, and that he presented the information more clearly. He then made an interesting move. Admitting that the privilege issued to the Van Langren family prohibited the imitation of their work “either bigger or smaller ... entirely or in part,” Hondius emphasized that this “is not understood [to mean] the rounding as such, in its appearance, or that no one could make a terrestrial globe, which are of course round.”³⁵ Hondius deliberately tried to limit the span of novelty to include only specific information on globes, forecasting the grim scenario that a strict observance of the Van Langren privilege would delay or even stop the growth and spread of geographical information. This argument in particular seems to have convinced the States-General, which decided to maintain Hondius’s privilege next to the existing one for the Van Langrens. The fact that the so-called “First Fleet” (1595–7) had just returned fairly intact from the East Indies, marking the beginnings of Dutch colonial expansion, undoubtedly played an important role. The authorities decided that the privilege for the Van Langrens would only be valid for a very specific use of rhumb lines, whereas the scope of Hondius’s privilege extended to the inclusion of new geographical information.

Determining the inventive step

At this point in time, two privileges on a similar object existed next to each other. As such, this was nothing exceptional. One could give numerous examples where different

34. Admittedly, there has been a lot of discussion over the recent decades on the fading distinction between discoveries and inventions in the context of biological patents on DNA sequences and plants; yet, from the perspective of the law, the essence of an invention is still a form of human interference, creating something that nature does not produce by itself in a specific configuration at the time when the patent is taken out. On the historical development of the so-called Product-of-Nature Doctrine, see also Christopher Beauchamp, “Patenting Nature: A Problem of History,” *Stanford Technology Law Review* 16, no. 2 (2013): 257–312; Daniel J. Kevles, “Inventions, Yes; Nature, No: The Products-of-Nature Doctrine From the American Colonies to the U.S. Courts,” *Perspectives on Science* 23, no. 1 (2014): 13–34.

35. “... grooter oft cleender ... in geheel ofte deel gelyck zynde. 27. Dat niet is te verstaen alleen vande rondheit, in aller schijn, ofte niemant geen weerelt clooten en zoude mogen maken, die natuurlick ront” *Cort Recueil*; PVDK, p.613 (note 11).

inventors obtained privileges to produce similar products, thereby effectively splitting up market control.³⁶ Moreover, the coexistence of several privileges on a similar object was not uncommon in the book industry, as Hondius himself did not fail to notice. He claimed that Van Langren “should have known from daily experience, which instructs him that many [people] often work in an art and publish their work in that art to be judged and used by everyone for its beauty, and that each one [of them], in order to be allowed to keep the profit of his work petitions, obtains, and defends a privilege.”³⁷

Printing privileges were similar to invention privileges in the sense that they transferred exclusive rights to individuals for the production, sale, and distribution of specific products for a limited period of time.³⁸ Whereas invention privileges related to technical advancement, printing privileges were issued for products that somehow involved the use of a printing press, such as books and engravings. Globes fell between two stools in this context, as they were first printed in the shape of gores using copperplate engravings and later affixed to wooden spheres. As an early form of legal hybrid, globes thus sat uneasily between invention privileges (issued for tridimensional objects) and privileges for printed products – a fact that Hondius cleverly tried to exploit.³⁹

36. In 1596, for instance, both Hendrick de Keyser (1565–1621) and Hendrick Jacobsz. Staets (ca. 1558–1630) received a privilege from the States-General for their invention of a new sort of slit covered by two valves (*oorgat*) to be made in fixed bridge decks, allowing ships to pass with a standing mast. On the implementation of this invention in the Dutch Republic, see Karel Davids, *The Rise and Decline of Dutch Technological Leadership: Technology, Economy and Culture in the Netherlands, 1350-1800*, Vol. 1 (Leiden: Brill, 2008), pp.85–6.

37. “... behoorde te verstaen uyt de dagelicxsche experientie, daer by hy onderrecht wort, dat vele teffens, dickwils in eene konste aerbeyden, ende alle haer werck inde selve conste uytgeven, omme van een yder geoordeelt ende gebruyckt te worden t’synen schoonste ende elck voor syn werck, ende omme t’profyt van syn werck te mogen behouden, Octroy versouckt, vercrycht ende diffendeert.” *Cort Recueil*; PVDK, p.611 (note 11). In contrast to the two “justifications” (*Verantwoordinge*), probably written earlier, the *Cort Recueil* (“short summary”) was directed directly to the father, Jacob Floris. Hence, the change in finite form from plural to singular.

38. Printing privileges were the precursors to our modern-day system of copyrights. On the history of these privileges in the Dutch Republic, see Paul Hoftijzer, “Nederlandse boekverkopersprivileges in de 17e en 18e eeuw,” *Jaarboek Nederlands Genootschap van Bibliofielen* (1993), pp.49–62; Chris Schriks, *Het kopijrecht, 16de tot 19de eeuw: Aanleidingen tot en gevolgen van boekprivileges en boekhandelsusanties, kopijrecht, verordeningen, boekenwetten en rechtspraak in het privaat-, publiek- en staatsdomein in de Nederlanden, met globale analoge ontwikkelingen in Frankrijk, Groot-Brittannië en het Heilig Roomse Rijk* (Zutphen: Walburg, 2004). On the intertwined history of invention privileges and printing privileges, see also Joanna Kostylo, “From Gunpowder to Print: The Common Origins of Copyright and Patent,” in Martin Kretschmer and Lionel Bently (eds.), *Privilege and Property. Essays on the History of Copyright* (Cambridge: Open Book, 2010), pp.21–50.

39. On legal hybrids, see Jerome Reichman, “Legal Hybrids Between the Patent and Copyright Paradigms,” *Columbia Law Review* 94 (1994): 2432–558. As Mario Biagioli has shown, globes could indeed be protected by both printing privileges and invention privileges. Mario Biagioli, “From Print to Patents: Living on Instruments in Early Modern Europe,” *History of Science* 44, no. 2 (2006): 139–86, 162.

Hondius was certainly right to argue that several printing privileges could be issued for the protection and distribution of a similar text.⁴⁰ Yet it was not just the content that counted in the process of securing exclusive ownership rights in printed material; it was the form that counted too. Printing privileges were always issued for a text set in a specific format, with a specific layout, or using a specific letter type, like a book printed in octavo or folio, using an Augustin font, and so on. The States of Holland, as a case in point, issued four privileges in the 1580s for the publication of a Deux-Aes Bible in folio.⁴¹ The only difference between the different editions was the number of illustrations that they contained, not the text of the translation. The importance of material conditions for the distribution of printing privileges came even more clearly to the fore when one publishing house managed to obtain an amendment to their privilege that extended the exclusive publication rights for their edition to formats other than folio. Contrary to what Hondius asserted in his case for globes, form did matter when it came to printing privileges.

In fact, the digression into the world of print was nothing but an evasive tactic. Hondius was not concerned with making a distinction between technical inventions (as patents) and printed materials (as copyright). What he was after was to limit the monopoly powers of a master patent by carefully identifying the inventive step in the crafting of Van Langren's globes.⁴² Today, the inventive step (or non-obviousness) is a crucial requirement for inventions to be eligible for a patent protection. If a person with ordinary skill can deduce an invention on the basis of what is already known to the public, for instance by making a minor improvement to an existing machine, the invention will not be considered worthy or innovative enough for legal protection. Hondius tried to make a similar argument to discredit his opponent. He plainly admitted that he had copied "a few little cartouches and ships" in the style of Van Langren, yet claimed that this did "not concern the nature of our dispute."⁴³ After all, the ships were only for decoration and not an essential part of the invention that Van Langren tried to protect by means of a privilege.⁴⁴ The invention only consisted of what Van Langren had contributed by way of new and useful knowledge to that which was already known within the borders of the Dutch

40. In this connection, Hondius made explicit reference to the many printing privileges for different translations of ancient and recent literature. Point 7 of his *Cort Recueil*: "quod majus est, in translationibus alcujus libri." PVDK, p.611 (note 11).

41. The Deux-Aes Bible was first printed in 1562; it is known as the first complete Bible (including both the Old and New Testament) printed in Dutch. The example here is taken from Herman de la Fontaine Verwey, *Uit de wereld van het boek II: Drukkers, liefhebbers en piraten in de zeventiende eeuw*, 2nd ed. (Amsterdam: Nico Isreal, 1980), pp.77–102; Isabella Henriette Van Eeghen, *De Amsterdamse boekhandel 1680-1725*, vol. 5 part 1 of *De boekhandel van de Republiek, 1572-1795* (Amsterdam: Scheltema & Holkema, 1978), p.194.

42. The objective of a master patent is to claim a particular subject matter in terms as broad as possible. Usually, later patent filings break out varying elements and elaborate on it in more detail. Continuing patent application can have a similar effect.

43. "wel is waar dat... eenige compartementgjens ende schipkens (die de conste van ons different niet anne en gaan) in dese globe gestelt syn." *Tweede Verantwoordinge*; PVDK, p.605 (note 11).

44. A "copyright" as we know it today did not exist at the turn of the seventeenth century; the idea that an author would have a right to protect the way in which he or she expressed him or herself was completely unheard of.

Figure 1. Hondius's rendition of the different rhumb lines. Dutch National Archives, The Hague, NL-HaNA 1.01.02, inv. no. 12550.28.

Republic. According to Hondius, that contribution was nil. Speaking of the rhumb lines that the Van Langrens claimed to have invented, Hondius reasoned that “It is true that they ... intended to improve these lines; but they have not done so as the attached example shows.”⁴⁵ To substantiate his claims, Hondius attached a drawing showing how the supposed invention in fact adversely affected existing knowledge (Figure 1). The Van

45. “Tis waer dat sy ... dese linien hebben willen verbeteren; maer hebben sulcx niet gedaen alsoo blijktt by dit exampel hier an gehecht.” Point 3 in the *Apologie*; PVDK, p.585 (note 11).

Langren did make an invention, to speak in modern terms, yet it was not a “useful” improvement and therefore the privilege should never have been granted in the first place.

The discussion regarding the rhumb lines shows that the inventive step was measured in terms of the envisioned utility of the invention. Although a notion of inventiveness did surface, there was no such thing as a doctrine of invention. This finding confirms the ideas of Mario Biagioli, who has argued that:

as a regime, the privilege had no need for the idea of the invention (as a category), nor did it have a conceptual or legal space to represent it even if such an idea were to be found in the inventor’s mind. In this sense, there was just nothing intellectual about the privilege. It was all about locality, materiality, and utility.⁴⁶

The emphasis on materiality shaped an ambiguous attitude toward originality (“non-obviousness”) that returned at other junctures in Hondius’s discourse as well. For example, Hondius emphasized the location of and his lack of access to Van Langren’s globe, arguing “that I have not had the work of my counterparty anywhere near at hand, which would have been necessary, had I tried to copy it.”⁴⁷ Instead, Hondius openly claimed to have used other sources, including the maps by Ludovico Teixeira, the cosmographer of the King of Spain, and information from several English explorers. Hondius’s point here was not to convince the authorities that he had sourced his information from abroad, or to show that he disposed of a large network. The fact that he had used other sources than Van Langren was crucial to substantiate the claim that his globe “was in substantial points a new invention.”⁴⁸ It was the final composition of the globe that was eventually rewarded with a privilege.

Similar arguments regarding the use of sources could be heard in the book industry too. In 1613, for instance, the Dordrecht printer Jacob Canin sent a notary to the house of his colleague in Amsterdam, Paulus van Ravesteijn, warning him to stop counterfeiting a Bible translation “in octavo with psalms and notes” for which the States-General had granted him a four-year privilege.⁴⁹ Van Ravesteijn simply retorted that the plaintiff could only claim damages if he “can prove that [I follow] his copy.”⁵⁰ The

46. Biagioli, “Patent Republic,” pp.1145–6 (note 4).

47. “... Dat ick het werck van myne partye noch by noch omtrent my hebbe gehad, in het maken van myne globe, ‘twelck gans noodich hadde geweest haddick ‘tselfe willen conterfeyten.” *Apologie*; PVDK, p.587 (note 11).

48. “... dat die voors. globus inde substantiele pointen zy eenen nieuwe inventie ” Claim to be found in the privilege, NL-HaNA, States-General, 1.01.02, inv. no. 12298, fol. 190; PvdK, p.577.

49. “... mette noten in forma van octavo....” J. G. C. A. Briels, *Zuidnederlandse boekdrukkers en boekverkopers in de Republiek der Verenigde Nederlanden omstreeks 1570-1630: een bijdrage tot de kennis van de geschiedenis van het boek* (Nieuwkoop: B. de Graaf, 1974), p.223.

50. “... so hij Canin kan bewijsen dat Ravensteijn syn copie volcht hij alsdan daerover schade lijden.” *Ibid.*

use of different sources for typesetting a text would result in a new product, while the use of new sources of geographical information would give rise to a new invention in the case of globes. In both instances the efforts involved in the process of production were rewarded with a privilege, not the degree of creativity or any flash of genius.

Just as the category of “invention” was fabricated by and through the law, the category of “inventorship” was constructed along the lines of legal conflict, in the course of which a specific use of language played a crucial role. Hondius never spoke in one register, but continually shifted the accent of his argument, making arguments of a legal, political, scientific, and religious nature. He accused Van Langren of being an Anabaptist and played a political game focusing on the economic importance of new knowledge. He did not hesitate to invoke the notion of “scientific advancement” as well. Hondius discredited Van Langren as an imposter who did not pay enough respect to the experts in the field, while creating a lineage of knowledge production that began with Ptolomaeus and ended with himself. By this type of boundary-work, Hondius substantiated the idea that growth of geographical knowledge was reliant on inventors to begin with.⁵¹ He thus met the requirements of the legal process, which favored the idea of innovation as a linear process that progressed over time.

Outcome and conclusion

The outcome of the conflict between Hondius and Van Langren was that the scope of claims in Dutch privileges securing exclusive ownership rights in globes became limited to the content that could be found on globes, and not to the globe as an object.⁵² Globes containing new information had a better utility and thus were different inventions. This line of argumentation had far-reaching implications for the dissemination of geographical knowledge, if only because other players in the Dutch Republic now entered the globe production market (not least, the famous cartographer Willem Jansz Bleau). A true upturn in the production of globes followed from the States-General’s decision, and globes made in the Republic would soon become recognized among the finest ever made.⁵³ From that perspective, it can be said that the 1597 decision by the States-General was pivotal in rendering the Dutch Republic into a center of European globe production in the seventeenth century.

51. I use the notion of boundary-work here, following Thomas F. Gieryn, “Boundary-Work and the Demarcation of Science from Non-Science: Strains and Interests in Professional Ideologies of Scientists,” *American Sociological Review* 48, no. 6 (1983): 781–95.

52. According to Peter van der Krogt, this made privileges for globes virtually useless; after all, by making (even the smallest) additions to existing knowledge, it would become possible to circumvent all accusations of piracy. That was the reason, according to Van der Krogt, that none of the Dutch globe-producing firms in the Dutch Republic petitioned for a privilege ever again until much later in the seventeenth century. Krogt, *Globi Neerlandici*, 1993, p.115 (note 11). Yet the addition of information did not prevent printers from soliciting for privileges in the book industry (one could think here of dictionaries, for example). Perhaps the divergence can also be explained by the fact that the material economy of globes was different from that of books, in the sense that it was easier to copy a typeset text than an engraving.

53. In the period 1597–1605, no less than seventeen new globes were produced in Amsterdam alone. *Ibid.*, pp.125–68.

Simultaneously, the case of *Van Langren v. Hondius* demonstrates how the law functioned as a technology ordering a complex web of knowledge and status claims. It shows how engagement with the legal notion of invention privileges intensified the felt need to demarcate the novel elements of an invention, pushing a notion of inventorship that was grafted on originality. Although there had always been the necessary conflict over issues of priority, these conflicts had ultimately belonged to the domain of honor, not law. Who had invented something had remained a matter of trust and opinion. Cases like *Van Langren v. Hondius*, however, made it necessary to define the issue of priority in a legal framework. Once in place, the internal operation of the law became one of the driving forces for wider developments.

One of the consequences was that attention shifted ever more clearly to identifying the “first and true inventor” instead of entertaining the notion of an invention being the outcome of a collective effort.⁵⁴ Only a first inventor, after all, could legally exclude others from using particular knowledge. The second consequence was that, in order to determine the scope of a privilege, the inventive step of an invention had to be narrowly defined. Even if, compared to today, there was a radical difference with regard to what could count as an inventive step, it was along these lines that the administrative practices entailed in the institution of invention privileges helped to shape the legal category of “novelty” in such a way that it became more akin to “originality.” Eventually kept in check by a robust notion of utility, the necessity to document the authorship of an invention brought about the obligation to demarcate the degree of inventiveness. The distribution of exclusive privileges in that way marked an important step in the making of modern patents, which have been from the beginning intrinsically connected to a floating notion of ingenuity.

54. There is a connection in this regard to writing about inventions, where it became ever more important to identify a unique inventor as well. For illustration, Polydore Vergil (c. 1470–1555) made an attempt to list all the ‘inventors’ of human activity. In his famous work *De Inventoribus Rerum* (1499), he spoke of everything from the invention of the law to the invention of money, and from the origins of agriculture to the beginnings of maritime navigation. At the end of chapter eight in book three, the author nevertheless admitted that there also had been many inventions that could not be attributed unambiguously to a single inventor (singling out, in particular, the famous ensemble of gunpowder, the compass, and the printing press). Moreover, a number of inventions were only made useful by incremental ameliorations, and not because of a big breakthrough. Vergil explicitly stated that he did not want to spend much time on these inventions, since it was better “to use few words in order to tell something certain than to use many to describe the uncertain” (*met weynighe woorden yets sekere te verhalen, als met veele onsekere dingen, te beschryven*). Polydorus Virgilius, *Waerachtige beschryvinghe. Inhoudende wie de eerste autheuren en vindere aller consten, inventien, en hantwercken sijn geweest*. Translated from Latin by E.M.G. (Amsterdam, sold by A. van den Heuvel, printed by B. de Wild, 1663), p.440. Instead, Vergil emphasized individual achievement and the importance of personal honor. For the broader context of Vergil’s work, see Catherine Atkinson, *Inventing Inventors in Renaissance Europe: Polydore Vergil’s De Inventoribus Rerum* (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2007).

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